

A Study on Different Variables on the Distribution law of Oil and Gas Diffusion Concentration of Internal Floating Roof Tanks

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Abstract

Internal floating roof tanks are used to store volatile, flammable, and explosive liquids, making the study of the distribution of oil vapor concentration in the gas space above the floating roof critical for safety management. This study developed a computational fluid dynamics (CFD) model based on the Realizable k- ϵ turbulence model to evaluate the effects of different liquid levels (low, medium, high) of the floating roof and external wind speeds on the oil vapor volume fraction. The results indicate that the oil vapor volume fraction above the floating roof decreases as the roof rises, suggesting that the increase in gas space leads to a more dispersed distribution of oil vapor. Additionally, external wind speed has a limited effect on the evaporation process and does not significantly influence the diffusion capacity of volatile oil vapor. Based on the explosion limits of gasoline and n-heptane, this study evaluates the safety of vapor concentration, providing important references for the safe management of storage tanks.

Keywords: Internal floating roof tank, Oil volume fraction, Vent, Oil and Gas diffusion, Numerical simulation

1. Introduction

With the advancement of maritime technology, oil transportation has gradually emerged as a vital sector. As a global strategic resource, oil plays a crucial role in modern economies and is widely used in transportation, energy, and manufacturing. [1] Despite the rapid development of the container shipping industry, oil is still primarily transported by sea and pipeline, with maritime transport dominating the sector. Consequently, the design of shipboard oil storage tanks increasingly focuses on oil and gas storage and evaporation control. Internal floating roof tanks (IFRT) have become the ideal choice for storing volatile, flammable, and explosive liquids due to their unique design, which overcomes the drawbacks of dome-shaped and external floating roof tanks. The floating roof effectively limits the contact area between the liquid and the gas, reducing evaporation losses, while the sealing ring further minimizes breathing losses and emissions of volatile organic compounds (VOCs). However, factors such as material fatigue, corrosive components, and inadequate maintenance may lead to increased evaporation and deterioration of oil quality. In recent years, the development of simulation technology has led to the widespread use of numerical modeling to study the distribution of oil vapor concentrations in internal floating roof tanks, making it a research hotspot. Foreign scholars have established a relatively comprehensive theoretical framework regarding floating roofs and sealing methods. Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) has been widely applied to research oil and gas release and diffusion phenomena, further advancing the field. These findings provide theoretical foundations and practical support for the design and optimization of internal floating roof tanks. Nikolaos

Stamoudis [2] and M. Hawk [3] developed and tested evaporation models for heavy fuel oil (HFO) using CFD methods, creating a 3D, turbulent, multiphase, multicomponent, and reactive flow field for simulating diesel evaporators. Kountouriotis et al. [4] utilized CFD to conduct numerical simulations of oil and gas leakage dispersion at gas stations, considering factors such as wind speed, direction, temperature, and leakage location. Masoud Rahimi et al. [5] performed CFD simulations on high-rise buildings, revealing uneven wind pressure distributions around tall structures. Zhao Jian et al. [6] investigated the impact of different oil recovery and transportation scenarios on the non-uniform physical fields within storage tanks using numerical simulations. Hassanvand et al. [7,8] employed the VOF model in CFD analysis software to simulate various factors affecting gasoline loading processes, examining how temperature, loading speed, and initial oil-gas concentration influenced the oil loss rate during loading. Ling Zhu et al. [9] found that wind forces could cause tank deformation or floating roof displacement, leading to oil-gas leakage into the secondary sealing space.

CFD numerical simulations of high-rise buildings have been performed by Asghar Alizadeh Dakhel et al. [10] Both results show that there is an inhomogeneous wind pressure distribution around high rise objects. Said et al. [11] conducted a 3D simulation and wind tunnel experiments comparing the flow characteristics around single and double cylindrical structures under varying wind speeds. They discovered that recirculation occurred near the leeward side of the first cylinder and that the distance between the two cylinders affected the shape and speed of the recirculation. Humphrey Pasley et al. [12] demonstrated through wind tunnel experiments that airflow passing over floating roof tanks creates a negative pressure zone around the tank wall's windward side, which is below the sealing space pressure. Raznahan et al. [13] developed a 3D numerical model of three-phase transient flow based on the Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes momentum equations for incompressible viscous fluids and the VOF method, finding that wave number, average flow velocity, and oil properties affect the diffusion range and oil volume fraction in open waters. Galeev et al. [14] compared results from experimental data and numerical simulations with those computed using the Mackey-Matsugu equation, finding that evaporation rates were more dependent on tank size at low wind speeds. Sikanen and Hostikka [15] investigated mass transfer and heat transfer characteristics of water surfaces during fires based on Stefan diffusion. Alireza Rouzbahani et al. [16] examined the effects of baffles on base shear, fluid sloshing height, overturning moments, and baffle forces, providing optimal perforation percentages for baffles in cylindrical tanks to reduce fluid sloshing height. Huang Weiqiu et al. [17] established an evaporation rate model for IFRTs and validated it with measured data from small IFRTs to assess liquid loss rates under various conditions. TAMADDONI et al. [18] experimentally studied VOC emissions during crude oil loading on tankers, analyzing how oil-gas component ratios, temperature, pressure, loading conditions, and duration influenced emissions. Okamoto et al. [19] researched changes in physical parameters like vapor pressure, evaporation rates, and flash points for gasoline and kerosene, proposing corresponding fitting formulas but noting a need for further studies on loss mechanisms related to tank operation characteristics. Zhang Gao et al. [20] conducted numerical simulations and wind tunnel experiments to analyze the effects of varying floating roof heights and wind speeds on oil vapor diffusion, concluding that the gas space volume of the IFRT and wind speed significantly impacted vapor loss rates, larger gas volumes led to weaker airflow exchange, facilitating vapor accumulation. By establishing a diffusion model for internal floating roof tanks (IFRTs) and utilizing numerical simulations, they studied the distribution and variation patterns of vapor mass fractions and pressure at different floating roof heights, finding that vapor mass fractions were lower near the tank top and the distribution was nearly symmetrical. As the floating roof height decreased, the vapor mass fraction in the mixed gas region of the tank gradually diminished, remaining below the lower explosive limit (LEL), indicating improved safety. Shuai Ji et al. [21] developed a mathematical model for large single-deck floating roof tanks and simulated the temperature and flow field changes during the oil heating process within the tank using FLUENT software. They analyzed energy and mass changes during the heating process from both temporal and spatial perspectives,

recommending the effective utilization rates of energy and heating as evaluation metrics for the tank heating process. Zhang Weifeng et al. [22] proposed a superhydrophobic coating to reduce crude oil loss and VOC emissions in petrochemical companies, significantly contributing to environmental sustainability. Alireza Doustvandi et al. [23] investigated the interactions between the movement of double-deck floating roofs and the fluid, as well as the connections between the roof and the tank shell, finding that seals between the floating roof and shell significantly increased liquid slosh damping and suppressed vertical displacement of the roof. Jan B. Haelssig et al. [24] linked mass transfer diffusion phenomena to leakage rates affected by external wind speed disturbances, achieving better agreement between simulation and experimental results. Their study revealed that wind disturbances around cylindrical structures created different pressure zones on the tank's outer wall and top, altering the internal oil-gas concentration, which involved turbulent issues. Huang Fengyu et al. [25] developed a computational method for simulating oil evaporation and subsequent vapor diffusion in IFRTs under unsteady conditions. Wei Yonghui et al. [26] utilized the CFD software FLUENT to model the advection-diffusion behavior of gas leaks from storage tanks, discovering that tank arrays significantly altered, resulting in a reduced advection-diffusion effect for downstream tank leaks compared to upstream ones. Liu Bin et al. [27] integrated CFD modeling with process simulation to comprehensively optimize key parameters, efficiently managing harmful substances and preventing oil-gas evaporation from storage tanks, which could lead to severe air pollution and safety hazards. Kim et al. [28,29] found that the RNG $k-\varepsilon$ turbulence model improved the simulation accuracy of turbulent vortex phenomena and performed well in modeling wind pressure distributions near walls. In summary, current research on internal floating roof tanks primarily focuses on floating roofs, sealing methods, and the evaporation and diffusion of oil and gas, with variables such as wind speed and liquid surface dimensions being considered. However, studies on the gas volume fraction within the tank, particularly under the combined effects of wind speed and liquid surface size, are relatively scarce. Therefore, there is an urgent need to strengthen the monitoring and research on the gas volume fraction within these tanks.

This study aims to investigate the distribution of gas volume fractions in internal floating roof tanks under varying wind speeds and liquid surface dimensions, addressing a significant gap in the literature. Such research will enhance our understanding of the operational status of internal floating roof tanks, improving their safety and economic efficiency. Additionally, it will contribute to reducing oil and gas losses, minimizing environmental pollution, and increasing tank safety. The findings from this research will provide strong support for the development of the petroleum and chemical industries and will further promote the optimization and improvement of tank technology.

2. Model analysis

2.1 Mathematical model

The working fluid within the internal floating roof tank (IFRT) is air, and the changes in the flow field can be described by establishing fundamental governing equations. These governing equations include the continuity equation, momentum conservation equation, and energy conservation equation. When wind blows toward the internal floating roof tank in a specific direction, the diffusion and migration of oil within the tank will be affected, necessitating the use of component transport equations for prediction and analysis. To investigate the heat transfer and mass transfer phenomena between air and oil vapor (multicomponent gas) under conditions without chemical reactions, it is essential to introduce the chemical species conservation equation. This equation describes the concentration changes of different components, ensuring accurate simulation of the diffusion behavior and transport processes of oil and gas during the study.

Mass Conservation Equation:

$$\frac{\partial(\rho\mu_i)}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Where ρ is the fluid density, and μ_i is the velocity component primarily describing convective mass transport.

Momentum Conservation Equation:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (\rho \mu_i \mu_j) = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (\mu_t \frac{\partial \mu_i}{\partial x_j}) + (\rho - \rho_a) g_i \quad (2)$$

Where p is pressure, μ_t is turbulent viscosity, and g_i is gravitational acceleration the velocity variables μ_i and μ_j describe convective transport and interactions of momentum.

Energy Conservation Equation:

$$\frac{\partial(\rho E)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho \mu_j E)}{\partial x_j} = \rho f_j \mu_j - \frac{\partial(p \mu_j)}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial(\tau_{ij} \mu_j)}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (k \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j}) + S_h \quad (3)$$

The energy E is:

$$E = h - \frac{p}{\rho} + \frac{\mu^2}{2} \quad (4)$$

Where f_j : volume force, T : temperature, k : fluid heat transfer coefficient, S_h : energy source term.

Component conservation equation:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho Y_i) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (\rho u_i Y_i) = -\frac{\partial j_i}{\partial x_j} + S_i \quad (5)$$

$$j_i = -\left(\rho D_{i,m} + \frac{\mu_t}{Sc_t}\right) \frac{\partial Y_i}{\partial x_i} \quad (6)$$

Where Y_i : local mass fraction of component I, j_i : diffusion flux of the i-th species, $D_{i,m}$: mass diffusion coefficient of substance i in the mixture, Sc_t : turbulent Schmidt number.

When the wind speed is greater than or equal to 2 m/s, the disturbance of the wind speed to the external floating roof tank is a typical turbulence problem. For this reason, the Realizable k- ϵ model is chosen for simulation and analysis. The model has good performance in dealing with flow separation and secondary flow. Compared with the traditional standard k- ϵ model, the Realizable k- ϵ model has two main improvements: first, a new formula is introduced for the turbulent viscosity to more accurately describe the change of the turbulent viscosity, second, a new dissipation rate transport equation is added, which can effectively solve the laminar flow velocity fluctuation problem, which is especially advantageous in predicting complex flow phenomena such as flow separation. This improvement makes the Realizable k- ϵ model more accurate and applicable in a wide range of turbulence simulations.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho k) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (\rho k u_j) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_k} \right) \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \right] + G_k + G_b - \rho \epsilon - Y_M + S_k \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho \epsilon) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (\rho \epsilon u_j) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_\epsilon} \right) \frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial x_j} \right] + \rho C_1 S_\epsilon - \rho C_2 \frac{\epsilon^2}{k + \sqrt{\nu \epsilon}} + C_{1\epsilon} \frac{\epsilon}{k} C_{3\epsilon} G_b + S_\epsilon \quad (8)$$

$$C_1 = \max[0.43, \frac{\eta}{\eta + 5}], \eta = S \frac{k}{\epsilon}, S = \sqrt{2 S_{ij} S_{ij}} \quad (9)$$

In the above equations, k represents the turbulent kinetic energy (m^2/s^2), and ϵ represents the turbulence energy dissipation rate (m^2/s^3). Additionally, G_k and G_b respectively represent the generation of turbulent kinetic energy due to mean velocity gradients and buoyancy ($kg \cdot m^{-1} \cdot s^{-1}$). Y_M denotes the contribution of fluctuating dilation in compressible turbulence to the overall dissipation rate ($kg \cdot m^{-1} \cdot s^{-1}$). C_1 and $C_{1\epsilon}$ are constants. σ_k and σ_ϵ are the turbulent Prandtl numbers for turbulent kinetic energy and dissipation rate, respectively. S_k denotes the source term for turbulent kinetic energy ($kg \cdot m^{-1} \cdot s^{-3}$), and S_ϵ denotes the source term for the dissipation rate ($kg \cdot m^{-1} \cdot s^{-4}$).

2.2 Physical model

The physical model is constructed by using 3D drawing software, as shown in Fig. 1. The model is an internal floating roof oil storage tank with a bottom diameter of 20 m and a height of 14.0 m. The direction

of atmospheric flow is set as the negative direction of the z-axis, the direction perpendicular to the x-axis on the horizontal plane is the z-axis direction, and the direction vertically upward is the y-axis direction. The area of the oil storage tank is the calculation area, and the $y = 0$ plane is set as the symmetry plane. The total number of meshes is 109,640 and the number of nodes is 142,865. In order to measure the rate of oil evaporation from the tank under different operating conditions, the inner floating roof storage tank (IFRT) is constructed at a scale of 1:1. The inner diameter, wall height, top height, and rim clearance of the modeled tank are 360 mm, 375 mm, 39 mm, and 6 mm, respectively. The vent sizes of the modeled tanks are designed according to the selection principles of the prototype tanks, as shown below:

$$B \geq 0.06D \quad (10)$$

The total effective venting area of the vents of the model tank is indicated by B in square meters (m^2), where D indicates the inside diameter of the tank in meters (m). The effective venting area of the vents of the model tank should be greater than $0.69 m^2$ and the number of vents should not be less than four. The final tank model was equipped with 5 vents, each 19 mm wide and 10 mm high. All vents were evenly distributed on the tank wall near the top of the tank to ensure effective ventilation.

In addition, four different floating roof plate heights, $y = 5 m$, $7 m$, $9 m$, and $11 m$ (y is the distance from the top of the tank to the floating roof plate), were used for the internal floating roof storage tank (IFRT) to study the distribution of the volume fraction of oil and gas at different heights.

Figure 1. Four different floating roof plate height tank models.

2.3 Meshing

The first step in a Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulation is to discretize the computational region into a grid. The form, quality, and size of the mesh can have an impact on the results, so the quality of

the mesh generation is critical for stable and accurate results. In CFD flow analysis, the analyzed area is usually divided into a finite number of grids. Mesh generation can be categorized into structured grid and unstructured grid, and the common types of meshes include hexahedron, tetrahedron, polyhedron and their deformed forms.

In this study, the unstructured grid is usually used for the numerical simulation of the flow phenomena with drastic changes. According to the complexity of the different structures of the inner floating roof tank, we applied different types of meshes for different regions, respectively. For example, for the geometrically regular areas such as the tank wall and tank bottom, we use structured meshes, which have more regular shapes and arrangements and are easier for mesh generation and quality control. For complex structures such as the inner floating roof, floating plate struts, and sealing devices, we used unstructured meshes that can adapt to the complex geometries due to the complex geometries of these areas. In addition, we encrypted the mesh in key areas such as the sealing area between the inner floating roof and the tank wall, and the interface between the floating plate and the oil contact, in order to improve the accuracy of the simulation. In this way, the mesh densities of different regions are effectively controlled, thus ensuring the accuracy and reliability of the numerical simulation., and more detailed mesh generation methods are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Mesh Conditions

Mesh Type	Polyhedral Mesher
Base Size	800mm
Number of Prism Layer	2
Prism Layer Stretching	1.5
Prism Layer Thickness	20%
Volumetric Relative size	30
Number of Volume Mesh Cells	109640

Figure 2 illustrates the meshing performed for the baseline model (resolution region of 7.7 m and a distance of 7 m from the floating roof to the top of the storage tank).

In order to obtain the effect of wind speed on the diffusion of the gas mixture inside the storage tank, a wind scenario was established and a wind scenario model was constructed for this purpose (Figure 3). In the presence of a wind scenario, the blocking ratio is usually used as a basis for setting the cross-sectional area of the computational domain. The blocking ratio γ_b is defined as follows:

$$\gamma_b = \frac{A_m}{A_c} \quad (11)$$

A_m and A_c denote the maximum windward area of the model and the cross-sectional area of the computational domain (both in m^2), respectively. According to related studies, if the obstruction rate is less than 5%, the simulation results of the flow field may not be affected by the boundary. However, smaller experimental models increase the difficulty of data measurement, which in turn leads to larger errors. In order to improve the measurement accuracy of the wind tunnel experiments, we increased the size of the water tank. The blockage rate of the model in the wind tunnel experiments was 6%, which was calculated from equation (11).

Figure 2. Model meshing

Figure 3. Wind tunnel scenario model

2.4. Mesh independence verification

To verify the mesh independence of the model, models with different numbers of meshes were established, as shown in Table. Figure 4 shows the effect of the number of meshes on the mass fraction of gasoline vapor. It can be seen from the figure that as the number of meshes increases, the impact of the number of meshes on the mass fraction becomes smaller. Therefore, the number of computational meshes for numerical simulation is 522,374. This verifies the mesh independence of the numerical model.

Table 2. Mesh quantity modeling

Number of Model	1	2	3	4	5
Number of Meshes	443776	496334	522374	553641	635214

Figure 4. Mesh independence verification

2.5 Boundary condition

In this study, it is necessary to reveal both the heat and mass transfer due to the interaction of gas mixtures (air and gasoline vapors, air and n-heptane vapors) inside the tanks, as well as the effect of the temperature outside the tanks as well as the wind speed on the gas mixtures inside the tanks. In order to analyze the heat and flow phenomena caused by the interaction of gas mixtures (air and gasoline vapors, air and n-heptane vapors) inside the tanks, the following flow-related boundary conditions are applied: the adherent condition (no-slip) is applied to all the wall surfaces, and the oil vapor passes through the rim formed between the floating roof and the tank wall surfaces (0.01 m in diameter) at a constant velocity (6.69×10^{-7} m/s) into the tank, and pressure boundary conditions were applied to the five vents at the outlet. The temperature boundary conditions are as follows: heat flow conditions corresponding to the convective heat transfer coefficient ($h=10$ W/m²K) are used on the tank wall surface, the IFRT surface inside the tank is kept at a constant temperature (286 K), and outlet conditions are used for the vents. The physical boundary conditions are detailed in Table 3 and 4.

Table 3. Simulate the required physical properties

Boundary	Condition
Space	There-dimensional
Fluid	Multi-component gas
Flow solver	Segregated
Equation of state	Constant Density
Viscous regime	Turbulence
Reynolds-averaged turbulence	Realizable k- ϵ
Reynolds Number	5.5×10^6
Prandtl Number	0.9
Schmidt Number	1

Table 4. Boundary Condition

	Locations/States	Parameters	Comments
Inlet(Air)	Speed entrance	4.36m/s,6.36m/s	Velocity-Inlet
Inlet	Gap between the floating deck and tank wall	3.88138×10^{-7} m/s	Velocity
Outlet	Free exit	101.325kPa	Pressure-Outlet
Wall	Tank bottom, wall, floating deck	0	No-slip
Mass fraction	saturated concentration of N-hexane	0.3	gap of the floating deck
Ambient	Outside of the tank	303K	Temperature

3. Results

In this study, numerical analyses of four models, including the baseline model, have been carried out based on the high degree of difference between gasoline and n-heptane filling in the storage tanks. These analyses revealed the heat and material transfer phenomena inside the oil storage tanks. By performing 16 numerical simulations with different working conditions, important parameters such as flow characteristics, velocity field, pressure field, and mass fraction of gasoline and n-heptane vapors in the air-oil vapor space were demonstrated.

By analyzing these results, this study explains the behavioral characteristics of air-gasoline vapor and air-n-heptane vapor, and explores the effect of external wind speed on the evaporation process of an internal floating roof oil tank. These findings provide an important basis for predicting environmental and explosion risks and further enhance the understanding of the safety of internal floating roof oil storage tanks.

3.1. Behavioral properties of gasoline vapor in the benchmark model

Inside Internal Floating-Roof Tanks (IFRTs), this study characterizes the behavior of oil vapors under the interaction of gas mixtures (air and gasoline vapors, air and n-heptane vapors). Particular attention was paid to the gap between the tanks and the inner floating roof, which was 0.01 m (i.e., 10 mm). Gasoline evaporated through this gap with a velocity of 3.8813×10^{-7} m/s

In this study, the total height of the storage tank is 14.7 m and the liquid gasoline (Gasoline) and n-heptane (Heptane) are filled up to 7 m. The total height of the storage tank is 14.7 m and the liquid gasoline (Gasoline) and n-heptane (Heptane) are filled to 7 m. Therefore, the height of the actual resolution zone is 7.7 meters filled with the gas mixture. These conditions form the basis of the baseline model and provide important parameter settings for subsequent numerical analysis.

3.1.1. Mass fraction distribution

As shown in Figures 5 and 9, gasoline vapor (Gasoline) and n-heptane (Heptane) maintain a mass fraction distribution of 0.3 in the small annular space between the floating roof and the outer wall of the tank. The mass fraction decreases as the gas rises vertically (i.e., toward the vent and top of the tank). At the same

time, gasoline vapor entering the 1-cm annular gap diffused inside the gas region, indicating that the diffusion of gasoline vapor in the air-filled gas region creates a fluid behavior. This phenomenon shows the hierarchy of gasoline vapor concentration (mass fraction).

In addition, Figures 6 to 8, Figures 10 to 12, show the diffusion of oil and gas at the sealing ring, where there is a clear interface between the oil and gas concentration and the air. Vertically, the concentration is higher on both sides of the tank, while the vent at the top of the tank concentrates the gas flow towards the center, resulting in gasoline vapors and gases inside the tank accumulating mainly on the surrounding walls. The observations also showed that the concentration (mass fraction) profiles of gasoline vapor and vapor gradually converged to symmetry as the position of the observation point rose.

This phenomenon can be explained in two ways. First, gasoline vapor enters the tank from the annular space of the floating roof and initially flows to the low-concentration region, and then as the diffusion process proceeds, a concentration gradient is gradually formed inside the tank. Second, the concentration distribution of gasoline is gradually reduced by wind speed as the location of the observation point rises, and the effect of wind speed can be almost completely ignored at the top.

Figure 5. Mass distribution of gasoline vapors on the tank wall (basic type) at a wind speed of 4.36 m/s.

Figure 6. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at $y=8\text{m}$ position of the storage tank under wind speed of 4.36m/s (basic type)

Figure 7. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at $y=10.5\text{m}$ position of the storage tank under wind speed of 4.36m/s (basic type)

Figure 8. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at $y=14\text{m}$ position of the storage tank under wind speed of 4.36m/s (basic type)

Figure 9. Mass distribution of gasoline vapors on the tank wall (basic type) at a wind speed of 6.36 m/s .

Figure 10. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at tank $y=8\text{m}$ location for wind speed of 6.36 m/s (basic)

Figure 11. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at tank $y=10.5\text{m}$ location for wind speed of 6.36 m/s (basic)

Figure 12. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at tank $y=14\text{m}$ location for wind speed of 6.36 m/s (basic)

Figures 6 to 8 and 10 to 12 show the distribution of the mass fraction of gasoline vapor in the x - z plane at different y positions ($y = 8\text{ m}$, 10.5 m , and 14 m) for different wind speeds. It can be seen that the mass fraction decreases as the position approaches the upper part of the tank, indicating that the gasoline vapors are mainly concentrated in the lower region of the tank and their concentration decreases with increasing height. In addition, these plots clearly show that the mass fraction distribution is almost symmetrical at all locations except the observation point at $y = 8\text{ m}$, indicating the uniformity and symmetry of gasoline vapor diffusion at different heights. At $y = 8\text{ m}$, with a wind speed of 4.36 m/s , the mass fraction of gasoline vapors reaches the highest value of 0.247 , respectively, which shows the high concentration of gasoline vapors accumulating in the lower altitude region and is strongly influenced by the external wind speed. As the height increases to $y = 10.5\text{ m}$, the mass fraction decreases significantly and is relatively less affected by the external wind speed, but still maintains a certain concentration level. At $y = 14\text{ m}$, near the top of the tank, the mass fraction further decreases to 0.009 , which is close to 0 , indicating that the concentration of vapors in the upper region of the tank is very low and is minimally affected by the outside wind speed. In addition, the figure shows that the gasoline vapor is mainly higher at the sides and lower in the middle. This distribution characteristic stems from the fact that gasoline vapors leak mainly from the annular space of the floating roof, resulting in the accumulation of vapors mainly on the sides of the tanks and relatively little diffusion in the middle part.

These results indicate that the gasoline vapors inside the tanks and the existence of a significant concentration gradient in the vertical direction and the symmetry of the distribution of mass fractions suggest that the flow and diffusion processes inside the tanks are relatively uniform and less affected by wind speed, and that this effect gradually increases with the increase of the observed height.

3.1.2. Pressure distribution

The pressure difference between the inside and outside of the annular gap (rim) formed between the floating roof and the tank wall in the storage tanks of the Department is the main cause of oil and gas leakage. The external pressure is mainly affected by factors such as wind speed, while the internal pressure is mainly affected by changes in vapor pressure.

Figure 13. Pressure distribution in the vicinity of the inner wall surface of a storage tank (basic type)

The pressure distribution inside the tank is shown in Figure 13. From the figure, it can be seen that the internal pressure varies between 3.447 kPa and 3.450 kPa, showing that the pressure distribution inside the tank is in a very stable state.

3.1.3. Evaluation of explosion stability caused by oil vapor inside oil tank

The volume ratio (or mass ratio) of vapor inside the oil storage tank relative to the air in the tank can be used to quantitatively estimate its safety. Representative standards that can define this safety are the Lower Explosive Limit (LEL) and Upper Explosive Limit (UEL), which are defined as follows.

Firstly, the LEL refers to the minimum concentration of a specific combustible gas in the air that can cause combustion. The LEL is a numerical value representing the volume ratio of explosive gas in the air. If the concentration is below the LEL, combustion is insufficient to occur. Secondly, the UEL refers to the maximum concentration of a specific combustible gas in the air that can cause combustion. The UEL is also a numerical value representing the volume ratio of explosive gas in the air. If the concentration exceeds the UEL, combustion becomes more likely to occur.

The flammable range here refers to the area between the LEL and UEL, within which a flame can form and an explosion may occur. Generally, the relationship between the volume fraction (%) and mass fraction of vapor is as follows:

$$MF_h = \frac{\rho_h \cdot VF_h}{[\rho_h \cdot VF_h] + [\rho_{air} \cdot (1 - VF_h)]} \quad (12)$$

Where MF_h : mass fraction of n-hexane, VF_h : volume fraction of n-hexane, ρ_h : density of n-hexane [3.65 kg/m³], ρ_{air} : density of air [1.23 kg/m³]

The condition that the LEL is met inside the storage tank is a very important factor for safety and other aspects. The UEL and LEL for gasoline and n-hexane are defined as shown in the table below. Generally, the lower/upper explosive limits defined by volume fraction are converted to mass fraction as shown in the table below:

Table 5. UEL and LEL of gasoline and n-hexane vapor

	LEL		UEL	
	[vol %]	[Mass fraction]	[vol %]	[Mass fraction]
Gasoline	1.4	0.0530	7.6	0.2447
Heptane	1.0	0.0290	6.7	0.1760

To more accurately observe the distribution of oil vapor mass fractions under different conditions, this study designed five vertical section observation locations, as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Vertical profile mass fraction measurement position

Figure 15. Mass fraction of gasoline vapor at points 1-5 at a wind speed of 4.36 m/s (basic)

Figure 16. Mass fraction of gasoline vapor at points 1-5 at a wind speed of 6.36 m/s (basic)

The distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction along the vertical direction (i.e., in the direction of the tank height) at each of the five locations of the gasoline storage tank is shown in Figures 15 to 16 for different wind speeds. The horizontal coordinate in the figure indicates the starting point (at 7 m) from which the volume fraction of gas mixture was measured from inside the tank, implying that the region from the bottom of the tank ($y = 0$ m) to the floating roof ($y = 7$ m) is filled with liquid gasoline, while the region from $y = 7$ m to $y = 14.7$ m is the region of gas mixture.

It can be seen from the figure that the gasoline vapors were below the lower explosive limit (LEL, 0.053) in terms of mass fraction from the floating roof to a height of 4 m (i.e., from 10.7 m above ground to the top of the tank) for wind speeds of 6.36 m/s and 4.36 m/s. These results indicate that the gasoline in the tank is within safe limits under current conditions, reducing the potential hazard.

3.2. Behavior characteristics of oil vapor in tanks at different float heights

In order to confirm the effect of the change of floating roof height on the diffusion pattern of oil vapor in the air in the mixed gas area, we will analyze the following four cases.

Table 6. Classification for 4-Cases of oil storage tank

	Height of Floating deck	Height of Mixed gas	Computational domain
CASE 1	11	3.7	3.7
CASE 2	9	5.7	5.7
CASE 3[Basic Model]	7	7.7	7.7
CASE 4	5	9.7	9.7

3.2.1. Gasoline vapor behavior characteristics of CASE-1

In order to predict the effect of floating roof plate operation on the thermal and material properties of gasoline vapors, the height of the floating roof in CASE-1 is 11 m above the ground, so the gas mixture region of oil vapor and air in the tank is 3 m. The qualitative results of the behavioral properties of the oil vapors in the tank in CASE-1 are almost similar to those of the basic model, CASE-3, and so the results, such as the mass fractions, will be demonstrated here to be the same as those of CASE-3 but will compare the UEL and LEL for the mass fraction view at position y with CASE-3.

Figure 17. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at a floating roof plate height of 11 m ($y=12$ m) at a wind speed of 4.36 m/s

Figure 18. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at a floating roof plate height of 11 m ($y=13$ m) at a wind speed of 4.36 m/s

Figure 19. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at a floating roof plate height of 11 m ($y=14$ m) at a wind speed of 4.36 m/s

Figure 20. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at a floating roof plate height of 11 m ($y=12$ m) at a wind speed of 6.36 m/s

Figure 21. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at a floating roof plate height of 11 m ($y=13$ m) at a wind speed of 6.36 m/s

Figure 22. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at a floating roof plate height of 11 m ($y=14$ m) at a wind speed of 6.36 m/s

Figures 17 to 19 and 20 to 22, respectively, show the distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction in the x - z section in the vertical direction (y -direction) at different locations ($y=1$ m, 12.5 m, 14 m) for different wind speeds (4.36 m/s, 6.36 m/s). It can be seen that the mass fraction gradually decreases as the gas mixture region approaches the exhaust ports located in the top cover, but the concentration of gasoline vapor is relatively high around the five exhaust ports. By comparing Figures 17 to 19 with Figures 20 to 22, it is found that the wind speed has a large effect on the distribution of the mass fraction of gasoline vapors, but not so large as to ignore the floating plate location. Based on these results, CASE-1 with a gas mixture area height of 3 meters is considered an unsuitable operating condition with respect to the LEL and UEL important for explosion safety.

3.2.2. Gasoline vapor behavior characteristics of CASE-2

In CASE-2, the height of the floating roof plate is 9 meters above ground level, so the gas mixture region is 5 meters. Figures 23 and 27 below illustrate the distribution of the overall mass fraction and show the distribution on the tank walls.

Figure 23. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction on the wall of CASE-2 tank at a wind speed of 4.36 m/s

Figure 24. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at a floating roof plate height of 9 m (y=10 m) under a wind speed of 4.36 m/s

Figure 25. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at a floating roof plate height of 9 m ($y=12.5$ m) under a wind speed of 4.36 m/s

Figure 26. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at a floating roof plate height of 9 m ($y=14$ m) under a wind speed of 4.36 m/s

Figure 27. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction on the wall of CASE-2 tank at a wind speed of 6.36 m/s

Figure 28. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at a floating roof plate height of 9 m ($y=10$ m) under a wind speed of 6.36 m/s

Figure 29. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at a floating roof plate height of 9 m ($y=12.5$ m) under a wind speed of 6.36 m/s

Figure 30. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at a floating roof plate height of 9 m ($y=14$ m) under a wind speed of 6.36 m/s

Figures 24 to 26 and 28 to 30, respectively, show the mass fraction of gasoline vapors in the x-z cross section at three different vertical heights ($y = 10$ m, 12.5 m, and 14 m) for different wind speeds (4.36 m/s, 6.36 m/s). As can be seen from the Figure, the model exhibits the same properties as the other models, in particular, it shows a symmetric distribution in the center of the cross-section.

3.2.3. Gasoline vapor behavior characteristics of CASE-4

CASE-4 is the state where the height of the floating roof is 5 meters and the height of the gas mixture area is 9 meters.

Figure 31. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at a floating roof plate height of 5 m ($y=6$ m) at a wind speed of 4.36 m/s

Figure 32. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at a floating roof plate height of 5 m ($y=10$ m) at a wind speed of 4.36 m/s

Figure 33. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at a floating roof plate height of 5 m ($y=14$ m) at a wind speed of 4.36 m/s

Figure 34. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at a floating roof plate height of 5 m ($y=6$ m) at a wind speed of 6.36 m/s

Figure 35. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at a floating roof plate height of 5 m ($y=10$ m) at a wind speed of 6.36 m/s

Figure 36. Distribution of gasoline vapor mass fraction at a floating roof plate height of 5 m ($y=14$ m) at a wind speed of 6.36 m/s

Figures 31 to 36 show the gasoline vapor distribution in CASE-4 in x-z sections for different wind speeds (4.36 m/s, 6.36 m/s) corresponding to $y=6$ m, 10m, and 14m, respectively. As mentioned earlier, from a qualitative point of view such as the trend of the mass distribution and comparing the differences with other CASEs, it is found that as the wind speed increases and the floating roof plate moves the same distance, the change in the rate of loss is relatively larger for the high floating roof plate than for the low floating roof plate.

3.3. Behavioral properties of n-heptane vapor in the baseline model

In Figures 37 and 41, n-hexane shows a mass fraction distribution of 0.3 in the narrow annular space between the floating roof and the tank wall. In Figures 38 to 40 and 42 to 44, As the gas moves upward vertically (toward the tank's vent and top), the mass fraction progressively decreases. Furthermore, gasoline vapor entering through a 1 cm annular gap diffuses within the gas region, illustrating that the diffusion of

gasoline vapor contributes to fluid behavior in the air-filled space. This observation highlights the stratified distribution of gasoline vapor concentration (mass fraction) within the gas area.

Figure 37. Mass distribution of n-heptane vapor on the tank wall at a wind speed of 4.36 m/s (basic type)

Figure 38. Distribution of n-heptane vapor mass fraction at the y=8m position of the storage tank at a wind speed of 4.36 m/s (basic type)

Figure 39. Distribution of n-heptane vapor mass fraction at the $y=10.5\text{m}$ position of the storage tank at a wind speed of 4.36 m/s (basic type)

Figure 40. Distribution of n-heptane vapor mass fraction at the $y=14\text{m}$ position of the storage tank at a wind speed of 4.36 m/s (basic type)

Figure 41. Mass distribution of n-heptane vapor on the tank wall at a wind speed of 6.36 m/s (basic type)

Figure 42. Distribution of n-heptane vapor mass fraction at the y=8m position of the storage tank at a wind speed of 6.36 m/s (basic type)

Figure 43. Distribution of n-heptane vapor mass fraction at the y=10.5m position of the storage tank at a wind speed of 6.36 m/s (basic type)

Figure 44. Distribution of n-heptane vapor mass fraction at the y=14m position of the storage tank at a wind speed of 6.36 m/s (basic type)

3.4 Prediction of UEL and LEL (gasoline and n-heptane) by Floating Top Height

Inside an oil storage tank, liquid oil evaporates due to a variety of physical and chemical factors, resulting in the formation of oil vapor. For this reason, this study assumes that there is a 1 cm gap between the tank wall and the Internal Floating Roof (IFR) of the storage tank and imposes different wind fields around the tank in order to induce the diffusion of oil vapors through this gap to the air-filled tank space (i.e., the upper part of the floating roof). With this assumption, the study aims to predict the effect of wind speed on the behavioral characteristics of gas mixtures (air + gasoline vapors, n-heptane vapors) in the upper region of the tank.

Based on the definitions of LEL (Lower Explosive Limit) and UEL (Upper Explosive Limit), this study predicts the LEL and UEL of gasoline and n-heptane in terms of mass fraction in order to assess the explosion risk and its stability inside the tank. Specifically, the LEL and UEL for gasoline vapor are 0.053 and 0.244, respectively, while those for n-heptane vapor are 0.029 and 0.176, respectively, for the mass fraction

of gasoline and n-heptane, respectively, and these parameters provide an important basis for subsequent safety assessment and design optimization.

Figure 45. Mass fraction of gasoline vapor at points 1-5 for a floating roof plate height of 11 m (CASE 1) at a wind speed of 4.36 m/s

Figure 46. Mass fraction of gasoline vapor at points 1-5 for a floating roof plate height of 11 m (CASE 2) at a wind speed of 6.36 m/s

Figure 47. Mass fraction of gasoline vapor at points 1-5 for a floating roof plate height of 9 m (CASE 2) at a wind speed of 4.36 m/s

Figure 48. Mass fraction of gasoline vapor at points 1-5 for a floating roof plate height of 9 m (CASE 2) at a wind speed of 6.36 m/s

Figure 49. Mass fraction of gasoline vapor at points 1-5 for a floating roof plate height of 5 m (CASE 4) at a wind speed of 4.36 m/s

Figure 50. Mass fraction of gasoline vapor at points 1-5 for a floating roof plate height of 5 m (CASE 4) at a wind speed of 6.36 m/s

Figure 51. Mass fraction of n-heptane vapor at points 1-5 at a wind speed of 4.36 m/s and a floating roof plate height of 11 m (CASE 1)

Figure 52. Mass fraction of n-heptane vapor at points 1-5 at a wind speed of 6.36 m/s and a floating roof plate height of 11 m (CASE 1)

Figure 53. Mass fraction of n-heptane vapor at points 1-5 at a wind speed of 4.36 m/s and a floating roof plate height of 9 m (CASE 2)

Figure 54. Mass fraction of n-heptane vapor at points 1-5 at a wind speed of 6.36 m/s and a floating roof plate height of 9 m (CASE 2)

Figure 55. Mass fraction of n-heptane vapor at points 1-5 at a wind speed of 4.36 m/s and a floating roof plate height of 5 m (CASE 4)

Figure 56. Mass fraction of n-heptane vapor at points 1-5 at a wind speed of 6.36 m/s and a floating roof plate height of 5 m (CASE 4)

As shown in Figures 45, 46, 51, and 52, the mass fraction of gasoline vapors exceeded the UEL over most of the gas mixture region ($y = 11 \text{ m}$ to 14.7 m), indicating a relatively high explosion potential. In particular, the mass fraction is almost close to 0.3 in the vertical direction below the exhaust port located in the center of the roof.

As shown in Figures 47 to 50 and 53 to 56, the vapor mass fraction in the gas mixture region of the tank decreases as the height of the floating roof decreases (liquid gasoline filling decreases), and the results show a distribution below the lowest explosion limit (LEL) at the y-axis height. In other words, the possibility of vapor-induced explosion is significantly reduced when the gasoline filling is less than half of the tank. By comparing the situation under different wind speeds, it is found that the effect of wind speed on the diffusion of oil vapor is much lower than the effect of the height of the floating plate on the diffusion of oil vapor. It can be seen that the five exhaust ports (vents) mounted on the roof of the tank help to ensure its stability.

4. Conclusions

In this thesis, numerical analysis is applied to determine the behavioral characteristics of gasoline and n-heptane vapors in the mixed gas region of an internal floating roof storage tank (IFRT) due to evaporation and diffusion of oil under steady state conditions. In order to predict the behavioral characteristics of gasoline and n-heptane vapors diffusing into the air in the mixed gas region inside the tank, we employ a CFD technique that simultaneously resolves the continuity, mass, momentum, energy, and chemical component equations based on the basic assumptions of three-dimensional, turbulent, steady state, and incompressible flow. From this study, we have derived the following results:

[1] Based on numerical simulations, we have investigated the oil vapor diffusion process in internal floating roof storage tanks (IFRTs) and identified the effect of floating roof height on the oil vapor diffusion phenomenon. Through these simulations, we reveal the material transfer law in the evaporation and diffusion process between oil vapor and air in IFRT.

[2] In internal floating roof tanks (IFRTs), evaporated gasoline vapor and n-heptane vapor diffuse horizontally mainly under the influence of gravity, showing obvious vertical stratification characteristics. Close to the vents, the mass fraction of oil vapor is higher, while the mass fraction of gasoline vapor and n-heptane vapor inside the storage tank decreases significantly after diffusion.

[3] The numerical results demonstrate the effect of the amount of oil inside the tank on the stability inside the tank by predicting the height of the floating disk (i.e., the change in the gas mixture region).

[4] Comparative analysis revealed that the diffusion of n-heptane and gasoline vapors are basically the same, however, the overall volume fraction of n-heptane vapors is slightly lower than that of gasoline, which may be due to the fact that the density of n-heptane is smaller than that of gasoline.

[5] The results show that the effect of wind speed on the diffusion range of the gas inside the tank is relatively small, much lower than the effect of the height of the floating roof plate on the diffusion.

[6] As the loss rate increases with the elevation of the floating plate and shows that the roof plate moves the same distance, the loss change is larger for the high roof plate than for the low roof plate.

Data availability

Data Availability Statement: All data are contained within the article.

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Conceptualization, J.C.L and Y.L., methodology, C.B.L, software, S.W.D and C.Z., formal analysis, X.X.Z, investigation, Y.L., resources, G.C., writing—original draft preparation, J.C.L, writing—review and editing, X.X.Z, visualization, C.B.L, supervision, C.Z., project administration, J.C.L, funding acquisition, G.C. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding

This research was funded by the “Hundred Outstanding Talents” Support Program of Jining University, a provincial-level key project in the field of natural sciences, grant number 2023ZYRC23.

Competing interests

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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